

The effect of diurnal rhythms on static and dynamic balance performance

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Abstract

Study aim: The purpose of this research was to examine the effects of different times of day on static and dynamic balance performance.

Material and methods: Thirty male individuals (age 22 ± 1.2 years, BMI 23.4 ± 1.3 kg/m², height 178.5 ± 6.52 cm) volunteered for the study. The participants performed static and dynamic balance tests at 10:00, 15:00, and 20:00. Static and dynamic balance were measured using Y Balance Test (YBT) and the Balance Error Scoring System (BESS). One-factor repeated measures ANOVA with the LSD post-hoc procedure was performed to examine balance changes in the morning, afternoon, and evening.

Results: Results indicated a significant difference in static balance scores at different times of day ($p < 0.05$). Post-hoc analysis indicates that mean of errors in afternoon exhibits significantly smaller than those of morning ($p = 0.024$), and evening ($p = 0.029$). Other results showed significant differences in dynamic balance at different times of day ($p < 0.05$). Post-hoc analysis indicates that means of reaching distance in afternoon exhibits significantly larger than those of morning ($p = 0.032$), and evening ($p = 0.026$).

Conclusions: The results provide strong evidence about the effect of different times of day on performance.

Keywords: Postural control – Sport performance – Center of gravity – Balance

Introduction

Balance has been examined from neurophysiological, biomechanical, and performance perspectives [8]. From the neurophysiological perspective, it requires coordination of input from visual, vestibular, and somatosensory systems, which results in a motor response by the central nervous system (CNS) [8]. From the biomechanical perspective, balance has been divided into static and dynamic types. Static balance is the attempt to keep the stability of the center of gravity (COG) within the base of support, which requires little muscular activity. Dynamic balance is the ability to maintain the COG within the base of support, which requires higher neuromuscular activity [18, 25, 30]. Measuring the center of pressure (COP) during various standing conditions such as single – or double-limb stance can be achieved using a force platform [15]. A force platform provides accurate information about postural control

through the calculation of COP or the point of application of the force distributed under the feet [9]. The ability to maintain balance is an essential part of daily activities. Postural control plays an important role in rehabilitation and sports [24].

There are many situations where a sudden stimulus causes loss of balance and injury. Thus, it is necessary to accurately assess balance in athletes/patients and identify the factors that can influence it [30]. These factors include age, gender, foot shape, and diurnal rhythms [12]. Many behavioral patterns and biological functions such as pulmonary function [23], core temperature [28], mood [1], reaction time [30], alertness and memory [16], and cognitive function [5] have been shown to be affected by diurnal rhythms. Understanding the contributing factors to balance performance in recreational athletes can provide implications on injury prevention and performance training.

The central master-clock in mammalian species, including humans, is the suprachiasmatic nuclei (SCN),

a paired structure in the hypothalamus with a volume just about 0.25 mm³ perinucleus [20, 26]. Within the mammalian SCN, a molecular oscillator keeps the clock oscillating at its normal pace. The basis of this oscillator is two inter-connected molecular feedback loops of clock gene expression, a detailed description of which is beyond the scope of this review though [2]. Time-of-day could also affect balance performance [8, 17, 19]. Variations in certain biological behaviors and psychological and physiological functions relative to time-of-day are known as circadian rhythms [4]. It has been suggested that sports performance has its own circadian rhythm and there may be a peak window for certain performance [4, 6]. There is evidence to suggest that fine motor control movements are better performed in the morning, while anaerobic performance, muscle strength, and muscle power are likely to reach the peak in the afternoon [4, 6]. New world record-breaking performance has been demonstrated by athletes competing in the early evening when the body temperature reaches the highest [6].

There are few studies on circadian rhythm effects on balance. Gribble et al. [8] claim that dynamic balance performance in the morning is better than the afternoon and evening performance. Zouabi et al. [31] observed no time-of-day effect on postural static and dynamic balance. Cagno et al. [3] claim that the static balance performance of rhythmic gymnasts does not change at any time of the day, but their dynamic balance performance reaches a peak in the morning. Complicated balance movements require more concentration and attention, and they are affected by sleep state [22]. Moreover, the change in body temperature is one of the main factors affecting circadian rhythm [28]. Not all athletic rhythms reach a peak at the same time of the day. "Simple" tasks that are not cognitively demanding tend to reach a peak in the evenings in parallel with the core temperature. However, "complicated" tasks involving a wider range of cognitive components tend to reach a peak in the morning and to show a significant decrease thereafter [3].

Few studies have been done on the effect of circadian rhythms on balance, and their results are inconsistent. Based on the relationships between balance, performance, and injury risks in athletic environments [13, 14], understanding the time-of-day effect on balance in recreational athletes can provide insights into using time-of-day as a parameter to optimize performance and reduce injury risks. Additionally, it can provide valuable information in research design and indicate whether we should include time-of-day as a control variable in assessing balance. The present research aims to fill this gap and use field assessment to examine the effects of time of day on static and dynamic balance. The results may be useful to coaches and athletes, as it can inform them of the best time of the day for exercise and allow them to plan their training to achieve maximum performance.

Material and methods

A health questionnaire was distributed among 50 male physical education students, of whom 30 subjects were randomly selected for the study (age 22 ± 1.2 years, BMI 23.4 ± 1.3 kg/m², height 178.5 ± 6.52 cm). The participants with one of the following conditions were excluded from the study [21]: multiple ankle sprains in the last year (3 times or more), ankle sprain in the last 6 months, multiple knee injuries in the last year (3 times or more), knee injury or surgery in the last year, multiple hip injury in the last year (3 times or more), hip injury or surgery in the last 6 months, multiple general anesthesia in lifetime (3 times or more), general anesthesia in the last 6 months, neurological deficit, disease or drug consumption that affects the nervous system, and signs of vestibular disorders (e.g. tinnitus, vertigo, and imbalance). One week before data collection, the participants were called to a laboratory where the research procedure was fully explained to them and they signed an informed consent form. Then they learned and practiced the Y Balance Test (YBT-lower quarter) and the Balance Error Scoring System (BESS). Participants practiced each test six times. The distance between the two trails was 30s. The subjects' height, weight, and BMI were recorded. In addition, leg length from anterior superior iliac spine to the medial malleolus was measured to normalize the data. The dominant leg of the subjects was determined in a football kicking task. Subjects were asked to sleep enough before the test and refrain from exercise and consumption of food or beverages for 2 hours before each testing session. Balance was assessed using YBT and BESS tests during 3 sessions in one day (at 10:00, 15:00, and 20:00).

Static balance

BESS was used to assess static balance. A recent review reported good validity and reliability for this test [27]. In BESS, static balance is performed on stable and unstable surfaces in three stances: double-leg stance with feet together, single-leg stance on the non-dominant leg, and a tandem stance in a heel-to-toe fashion. The stances are performed with the eyes closed and hands on hips with errors counted during each 20-second trial [29]. Errors include:

1. Opening the eyes
2. Lifting hands off hips
3. Stepping
4. Stumbling or falling out of position
5. Lifting forefoot or heel
6. Abducting the hip by more than 30°
7. Failing to return to the test position in more than 5 seconds.

The unstable surface was a 50 × 41 × 6 cm foam pad. Stable surface was a piece of carpet.

Dynamic balance

YBT was used to assess dynamic balance. A reliability of 0.99 to 1 has been reported for this test [10, 11]. In YBT, reach-distance is measured in 3 different directions, i.e., anterior, posteromedial and posterolateral. If the left foot is the dominant extremity, the test is performed clockwise and vice versa [11, 27]. Eight participants were left-footed and the rest were right-footed. Figure 1 provides an outline of YBT and rotation direction based on the dominant foot. Figure 2 shows the YBT test kit where the posteromedial and posterolateral directions are aligned at a 135° angle to the anterior direction, while posteromedial and posterolateral directions form a 90° angle (these directions have been taken from the Star Excursion Balance Test).

The participants were required to stand barefoot on an elevated central plastic footplate and push a rectangular reach indicator block with the foot along each of the

three directions which was randomly selected by the rater. Trials were classified as invalid if the participants moved their foot from the footplate, applied enough weight through the reach foot so as to increase reach distance, or fell. Reach-distance was measured as the distance from the starting point to the point of maximum reach as shown by the indicator. Participants performed six practice trials in each direction to decrease the learning effect. Each participant performed three trials in each direction and their mean was calculated, divided by leg length (in cm), and multiplied by 100 to yield the reach-distance as a percentage of leg length [11, 27]. In addition to individual scores for each direction, a composite score was calculated using the following formula and was used in statistical analyses as dynamic balance score:

$$\text{Composite score} = \frac{(\text{Anterior} + \text{Posteromedial} + \text{Posterolateral})}{(3 \times \text{Limb Length})} \times 100$$

Figure 1. An outline of the YBT and rotation direction based on the dominant foot

Figure 2. Setup for the YBT test

In dynamic balance, the mean reaching distance and in static balance, the number of errors was calculated. One-factor repeated measures ANOVA with the LSD post-hoc procedure was performed to examine balance changes in the morning, afternoon and evening. Statistical analysis was performed with SPSS 22.

Results

The results of Shapiro-Wilk test indicated that the data were normally distributed ($p > 0.05$). Figure 3 shows the results related to the average number of errors in the static balance test at different times of the day.

The results of one-way ANOVA with repeated measures indicated a significant difference in balance scores at different times of the day ($F_{2, 58} = 10.87$, $\eta^2 = 0.31$, $p < 0.001$). Post-hoc analysis indicates that means of errors in afternoon exhibits significantly smaller than those of morning ($p = 0.024$), and evening ($p = 0.029$). Figure 3 shows that the participants' performance was better in the afternoon than in the morning and the evening.

Figure 4 shows the results related to the reach-distance at different times of the day. The results of repeated measures ANOVA indicated significant differences in dynamic balance at different times of the day ($F_{2, 58} = 364.39$, $\eta^2 = 0.21$, $p < 0.001$). Post-hoc analysis indicates that means of reaching distance in afternoon exhibits significantly larger than the morning ($p = 0.032$), and evening

($p = 0.026$). Figure 4 shows better balance performance in the afternoon than the morning and evening.

Discussion

The purpose of this research was to investigate changes in static and dynamic balance at different times of the day. The results showed that time of the day had a significant effect on static and dynamic balance performance. Little research has been carried out on the effect of diurnal rhythms of balance performance and most studies have focused on sleep disorder and balance. In this research, the participants were instructed to sleep enough the night before the test to provide a better estimate of balance performance. Maintaining a stable base of support during balance tasks requires the coordination of input from visual, vestibular, and somatosensory systems [23]. In a static balance task, the goal is to minimize displacement of the center of pressure, which does not need much muscular activity and mainly depends on the coordination of sensory information. The goal in a dynamic balance task is to maximize reach-distance value while maintaining unilateral support which requires more muscular contractions. Although goals are different in static and dynamic balance, the mechanisms for controlling the center of pressure are both affected by the time of the day [7].

The results of this study showed that static balance performance is better in the afternoon than in the

Figure3. Mean of number of errors in static balance test at morning, afternoon and evening

Figure 4. Reaching distance (cm) in dynamic balance test at different times of the day

morning or evening. The average number of errors was 15.8 ± 1.58 in the morning, 13.40 ± 1.75 in the afternoon, and 15.33 ± 2.11 in the evening. Among few relevant studies, none has reported significant changes in static balance performance at different time of the day. Gribble et al. [8] examined the effect of time of the day on static and dynamic balance using a force plate. They found that time of day had an inconsistent influence on static postural control. The researchers attributed this result to the learning effect resulting from 2 consecutive days of performing the task. Another reason was the lack of practice trials which led to the development of a learning effect across the two days of the study. In the present research, however, measurements were performed in a single day and the participants performed several practice trials to prevent the learning effect and task novelty on the testing day. The present findings also showed that dynamic balance performance was better in the afternoon than in the morning or evening. The mean reach distance in the dynamic balance test was 106.03 ± 2.52 cm in the morning, 116.97 ± 2.09 cm in the afternoon, and 105.37 ± 1.94 in the evening. As mentioned, the goal of the dynamic balance was to maximize reach-distance value while maintaining unilateral support, which requires the recruitment of muscular contraction and neuromuscular control through proper joint positioning [6]. Our finding is inconsistent with the results of Gribble et al. [8] who reported better dynamic balance performance in the morning compared to the afternoon and evening. The researchers assessed dynamic balance using the anterior reach of SEBT which is performed in eight directions.

While the results indicated better balance in the morning, improvement was seen only in the female participants. This was attributed to the use of a quadriceps-dominant pattern of knee control by women, while men tended to recruit more hamstrings [4]. Therefore, using only one direction of the SEBT and gender differences are two major flaws in Gribble et al. [8]. However, the present research used YBT to assess dynamic balance which includes three directions from SEBT, i.e., anterior, posteromedial, and posterolateral, which can provide a better assessment of dynamic balance performance. Another advantage of the present research compared to Gribble et al. [8] is that we only examined male participants so as to avoid differences in the recruitment of muscular contraction.

The major difference between the current and previous studies [17, 19] was the participant population. In the current study, the improved balance performance in the afternoon compared with the morning may be related to participants' sports experience and regular participation in physical activity. Certain sports performance including strength and power have been shown to follow the circadian body temperature curve and typically peak in the late afternoon or early evening [4, 6]. Previous studies have suggested that regular training at a specific time of the day may increase the performance then [4]. Midway through our data collection, we found that they normally exercised in the afternoon or the evening. Improved balance performance in the afternoon might be due to their body's acclimation of exercising. Sports participation may create different circadian rhythms and contribute to the

difference in time-of-day effect on balance in recreational athletes compared with the general population.

The results of the current study have implications for both clinicians and researchers. Balance assessments can provide useful information regarding athletic performance, injury risks, and severity of injuries [13, 14]. The findings suggest that dynamic balance is minimally affected by time-of-day, while static balance is affected to a certain degree by time-of-day in recreational athletes. Time-of-day may be considered as a factor in designing training programs to improve balance. In addition, longitudinal and intervention studies may need to include time-of-day as a control factor, especially for static balance. If the time of the day of testing are not controlled and changes in balance performance before and after an intervention is within the difference observed in the current study, it will raise questions about whether it is an intervention effect or a time-of-day effect. Given the present findings, exercise sessions in the afternoon are recommended for amateur athletes who are learning sports skills in order to improve balance performance. Moreover, due to the effect of different times of day on static and dynamic balance, fitness centers and sports clubs are recommended to assess static and dynamic postural control at specific times of the day, especially when data collection takes several days. Several limitations existed in the current study. The major limitation of the current study was a potential learning effect that confounded the time-of-day effect. Although the design of the current study was similar to the two previous studies [1, 17], other potential strategies contribute to the minimization of the learning effect. These strategies include counterbalancing the morning and the afternoon testing sessions among participants and more practice trials or sessions. Although the current study was conducted over a day, using more than two days to evaluate balance performance would also be more beneficial for differentiating the time-of-day effect from the learning effect. The effect of fatigue was not quantified and might have decreased the time-of-day and between day effects observed in the current study, even though the testing conditions were randomized and participants received adequate rest between trials and sessions. Different from previous studies [17–19] when participants were tested at a specific time in the morning or the afternoon, we tested our participants within an hour during a 3-h window in the morning, afternoon and evening. While the lack of control of the testing time may introduce confounding factors, it may increase the generalizability to the real world, during which sports activities were usually performed in a time window instead of a specific time. In general, time-of-day had a minimal effect on dynamic balance and a noticeable effect on static balance in recreational athletes. Participants demonstrated increased static balance performance in the afternoon compared with the morning. Time-of-day may

be considered as a factor in designing training programs for improving balance in recreational athletes. Longitudinal and intervention studies may need to include time-of-day as a control factor, especially for static balance.

Conflict of interest: Authors state no conflict of interest.

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